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Risk Management Strategies on Farm Outputs among Small-Scale Poultry Farmers in Corcuera, Romblon, Philippines

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Abstract

Poultry farming is known widely all over the country, especially since it is considered a source of income for Filipino farmers. This study was conducted to find out the risk management and determinants of farm outputs among small scale poultry farmers. This study used the descriptive method of research to gather information about the risk management and determinants of farm outputs among small scale poultry farmers in municipality of Corcuera, Romblon. There are 100 poultry farmers involved in the study. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents, it comprises 50% male and 50% female with an age ranging from 51-60 years old and 70% of them were married. In terms of household size, 52% have 4-7 members. For their source of income 72% were poultry farming and 95% has an income of P5000-10000 monthly. 47% of the respondents are elementary graduate and 84% of them were poultry farming for 5 years and above. 83% of the respondents have native chicken as their type of chicken in their poultry farm. Most of the respondents agreed on the different risks in managing poultry such as; environmental risk, production risks, health risks, market risk, and financial risk. There are determinants identified such as outbreak of disease, poultry facilities, veterinary care, supply of electricity and water, inadequate knowledge on poultry husbandry, and lastly high price of feed. Most of the respondents agreed that these interventions and strategies must be applied in managing the small-scale poultry. Such intervention stated are; promoting quality of poultry products, maintaining poultry health and sanitation, having strong communication and coordination between all those involved in poultry veterinary service, allowing plenty of sunlight and ventilation and allowing plenty of sunlight and ventilation, having personal saving, investing in quality feeds, biosecurity obtained and good drainage system.

Keywords: financial risk, intervention, poultry farmers, products, strategies

1.0 Introduction

Keeping poultry contributes ample development to household food security, the economic contribution to the province, and the country in general. It helps diversify income and provides quality food, energy, fertilizer, and a renewable asset in over 80 percent of the rural household. It also creates substantial income-generating activity for the poultry farmer from sales of birds and eggs as a valuable source of protein in the diet (Falculan, 2021). Notwithstanding its contribution to food security, poverty reduction and growth of economy, the industry is cumbered with numerous constraints which include competition between food and feed, dependence on the importation of exotic breed, drought, outbreak of diseases, high cost of inputs, low-quality chicks, inadequate market, etc. (Abigail Gbemisola Adeyonu, Abiodun O. Otunaiya, Enoch O. Oyawoye & Funmilayo A. Okeniyi, 2021).

2.0 Poultry Risk Factor: Review of Literature

The poultry sector experiences many problems such as rise in the price of feed and feed ingredients, avian influenza and other virulent diseases, floods, poor outputs, fluctuation of output prices, the global financial crisis, inadequate credit and low level of production specialization Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 2006. Entrepreneurs are somewhat scared to start for fear of bankruptcy. Adeyemo and Onikoyi (2012) stated that a number of periods of price uncertainty and movement (volatility) have caused the enterprise to fall into bankruptcy due to colossal loss in monetary value, farmers leaving the business and consumers facing ever increasing costs of food (chickens and eggs), consequently resulting in decline in the growth of the poultry sector. The danger created by risk and uncertainties is huge: it results in impressive loss of money, psychological displacement, complete business failure, etc.; thus, risk management becomes imperative. Legesse and Drake (2005) have defined risk as the influence of an undesirable result which occurs due to natural or human action. According to Kahan (2013), risks in livestock farming can be classified into: production (drought, heavy rainfall and diseases and pests); marketing (supply/cost of inputs, demand for a product/price and cost of production); financial risk (loan and its cost); institutional (change in policy at the local, national and international levels) and personal/human (accidents, illness, civil unrest and death). Appropriate risk perception remains a key factor in the choice of effective risk management strategy. The reason being that for a farmer to be able to manage risk effectively, awareness of the various prevailing risk factors faced becomes relevant. There is the need for the farmers to be knowledgeable about risk and acquire risk management skills that will help to identify problems and mitigate outcomes. Therefore, investigations of farmers' risk perceptions are of great importance in farm risk management. The farmer is in the best position to know the aspect, attributes and extent of the risks that affect his farm business. He is also saddled with the responsibility of evaluating the management strategies available to deal with risks. It is the responsibility of the farmer to take the appropriate decisions to manage the risks associated with agricultural enterprise.

3.0 Methods

The study used the descriptive method of research to gather information about the risk management and determinants of farm outputs among small scale poultry farmers in municipality of Corcuera, Romblon. This method as define by Aquino (2003), seeks to describe systematically a situation or area of interest factually and accurately. This covers 100 respondents which is composed of small-scale poultry farmers and poultry owner in the Municipality of Corcuera, Romblon. No sampling method was used to determine the number of respondents. The survey questionnaire will be the major instrument used in gathering the data needed. Construction of the Questionnaire. The questionnaire used in this study is the product of the researchers reading. The first draft will be constructed and showed to the researchers' adviser who went through each item based from the statement of the problem. Modifications will be done to ensure that each item would yield the information needed. The corrections and suggestions given by the adviser will be incorporated in the revision of the questionnaire. Afterwards, it will be again submitted to the adviser. After going through the questionnaire, the researchers will be advised to prepare copies for validation. Validation of the Questionnaire. Consultation with the thesis adviser and expert from the field of agriculture was undertaken to ensure that no item was similar or duplicated. The instrument will be presented to some thesis expert for comments, suggestions and recommendations. Administration of the Questionnaire. The questionnaire will personally be distributed by researchers to the respondents. Retrieval will personally be done by the researcher. Scoring of Responses. The items in the questionnaire were scored based on Likert scale with five as the highest score and one as the lowest score. Equivalent verbal interpretation was also provided.

4.0 Results

4.1 Respondents Profile

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Poultry farmer mean age of the farmers was about 51 years which is an indication that respondents were relatively in their middle age. The respondents were asked to indicate their sexes on the questionnaire. A result both male and female (about 50%) signifies that poultry farmers were not gender sensitive, this resulted to both sexes engaged in poultry farming. As a contradictory statement by Reyes (2000), stated that married man /woman experiencing some difficulties in their lives because of these difficulties they tend to find some alternative to be able to survive. 47 % respondents were elementary graduate on the level of education. Oladeji (2010) reported that maximum percentage of the poultry farmers (47%) had elementary school level education, followed by higher secondary level (28%). Majority (4-7 members) had the number on the family with fifty two percent (52%) which is considered as medium to large size family. The data given reveals that majority of poultry farmers source of income (76%) were practicing poultry farming as their main occupation, followed by other form of agriculture production (24%). Further reveals that majority of poultry farmers (776%) adopted poultry farming as primary occupation. This finding agreed with the finding of Babu (2013). He reported that native chicken farming was primary occupation of 83 per cent respondents, while secondary occupation of 83 per cent respondents. Mandal et al. (2006) reported different finding from this. He reported that majority of farmers (52.92 %) had labor as major occupation, followed by agriculture (22.5 %), animal husbandry (14.58 %), business (7.08 %) and service (2.92 %). Respondent's monthly income ranges from P5001-P10000 with a frequency of 95 and obtained a percentage of 95% while having monthly income of P15,000-P20,000 got the lowest frequency of 1 and a percentage of 1. This indicated that the most of the respondents have the monthly income of P5,000-P10,000 from poultry production. In terms of years of poultry farming, 5 years above got 84 which is the highest frequency with a percentage of 85% while 3-4 years got the lowest frequency of 2 and a percentage of 2. This means that most of the respondents were having their poultry farming for 5 years and above in the municipality.

4.2 Risk determinants

Financial risks, loss of capital got a weighted of 3.98, inadequate management obtained a weighted mean of 3.91, debt loan got a weighted mean of 3.89. This was supported by the study of Doward et al., (2007) that using debt to fund agribusiness investments, crop seasonality, and unlimited savings exposes a company or business to financial or liquidity risk. Movement in stock prices with a weighted mean of 3.74 in which the respondents agreed. high initial investment obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.15 and the respondent responded neutral. The overall average weighted mean in the financial risks was 3.53 in which the respondents agreed. This implied that this risk should be acknowledged by the poultry owner or those planning to have this kind of business should consider is their financial stability. Risk in management of small-scale poultry in terms of environmental; climate change obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.98, noise got a weighted mean of 3.96, poor quality water with a weighted of 3.94, and use patterns and chemical pollution both obtained a weighted mean of 3.93 in which the respondents agreed. These environmental risks gathered total average weighted mean of 3.53 in which interpreted that respondents agreed which was related to the study of Akinbile et al. (2013) which identified vaccination failures and lack of water and feed as the top three climate-related risks facing poultry farmers. The study also shows a positive correlation between farmers' risk perceptions of climate change and the management strategies adopted. Moreover, risk in managing the small-scale poultry is the health risk. The respondents agreed on the following health risks like disease-causing microbes with a weighted of 3.97, lack of access to health care got 3.88 nutritional deficiencies and impacted crop 3.87, foodborne illness 3.85, and infectious diseases from the poultry obtained a weighted mean of 3.54. In terms of health risks, the total average weighted was 3.82 and the respondents agreed. This implied that this type of risk was encountered by the respondents and they were aware about the health of their poultry as well as its effects to the health of themselves and this was supported by the study of Attian (2005) described that consumer confidence, product quality and safety, product variety, disease outbreaks and relapses will continue to pose major challenges to the poultry immunity, health and production. Likewise, production risk is one also the risk management for small-scale poultry. The following are the productions risks in which the respondents agreed.

4.3 Ways how to manage risks

Ways how the small-scale poultry farmers managed the risk when poultry diseases outbreak. As seen in the table, respondents strongly agreed in order to managed well the poultry must be clean and disinfected which obtained a weighted mean of 4.30. Respondents agreed on the others ways on how to managed the poultry such as; increased bird resistance through immunization procedures got a weighted mean of 4.15, providing a nutritious diet and plenty of water which got a weighted of 4.00, separating multiage of poultry birds, proper sanitation and isolation of sick poultry which both obtained a weighted mean of 3.99. Another procedure in identifying and treating sick poultry got a weighted mean of 3.98, vaccination with a weighted mean of 3.97, medication got 3.85. Adeyonu (2021) that farmers should employ disease prevention and financial management strategies to reduce the impact of various risks. Lastly, recalling chicken food item with the lowest weighted mean of 3.60 in which the respondents agreed. The overall weighted mean got 3.98 which means the respondents agreed on the ways on how the poultry will be manage when the risk strikes individual. This implied that the respondents were aware on how to cope up when a risk came up, they had their ways on how to manage it well. This was concluded by the study of Effiong et al. (2014) loosening pens and administering medicines and vaccines in a timely manner are key control strategies for poultry farmers, according to the report.

5.0 Conclusion

Most of the respondents agreed on the different risks in managing scale in the Municipality of Corcuera, Romblon such as environmental risk, production risks, health risks, market risk, and financial risk. There are determinants were identified such as outbreak of disease, poultry facilities, veterinary care, supply of electricity and water, inadequate knowledge on poultry husbandry, and lastly high price of feed. Most of the respondents agreed that these interventions and strategies were done in managing the small-scale poultry properly in Corcuera, Romblon such as; promoting quality of poultry products, maintaining poultry health and sanitation, having strong communication and coordination between all those involved in poultry veterinary service, allowing plenty of sunlight and ventilation and allowing plenty of sunlight and ventilation, having personal saving, investing in quality feeds, biosecurity obtained and good drainage system.

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